

PECULIARITIES AND DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF LOCATIONAL PREPOSITIONAL PHRASES IN THE SENTENCES

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to investigate the difference between locational syntactical-semantic prepositional phrases from the other prepositional units that are concerning with links with processuality of verbs and substantivity of nouns. Taken all prepositions related locative syntaxeme in the novel "The Time Machine" by Herbert Wells, they are analysed with different types of locativeness by the exploiting examples in the work. This study represents distinctive and similar features of locative category with giving clear samples. The analyse shows the accurate principles of locative syntaxemes in the sentences.

Introduction. In the English language it can be seen various locational prepositional phrases in sentences, which represent important features of understanding of prepositional phrases being most common in the usage of the sentence. They denote various syntactical and semantic meaning in accordance with which of locational prepositions being used. They were started to use in English in the long term. It was started to utilize locational prepositions in Old and Middle English. Some linguists revealed various features of locative semas they were identified their similar and distinctive features, syntactical and semantic positions, compared to different version of sentences. They represented "use-types" of prepositions by dividing them different groups with different pragmatic meaning. However, prepositions were deeply explored as a prepositional phrase in the works of linguists A.M. Mukhin, O.S.

Akhmanova and L.N. Badanina. These linguists studied theoretical and practical aspects of prepositions with the category of locativity in the sentence, which was defined specific semantic and syntactic peculiarities of them accordingly. They assumed that prepositional locative semas could be distinguished from various words depending on verbs and nouns, and doing analysis of different types with locative phrases through sentences. By looking through various kinds of prepositional phrases with locative category, we can identify locational prepositional syntaxeme by investigating and finding the difference from the other prepositional phrases.

Literature review. Locational prepositional phrases are a word group associated with lexical correlation and grammatical combination of verbs and nouns, which are interrelated with different prepositions. Locational prepositions depict the place, direction,

movement, transition and instrumentality where a certain person or thing is. According to this, locative signs of prepositions are showed with different way. So they are divided into some types. They are locative adessive, locative allative, locative ablative, locative translative and locative instrumentality.

Locative adessive semas express the exact place of a person or a thing, which is in this location happening any actions. They show a clear attitude of placement with locative adessive semas, they are appeared precise image of absolute certainty of the place. Locative adessive sema includes different prepositions, such as at, in, in front of, before, behind, on, across, under, beneath, by, over, to, above.

He had a small camera under one arm and a knapsack under the other.

I fancied I could even feel the hollowness of the ground beneath my feet.

Coming through the bushes by the White Sphinx were the heads and shoulders of men running.

The rebounding, dancing hail hung in a cloud over the machine.

They taught you at school is founded on a misconception.

You know how on a flat surface, which has only two dimensions.

He set it in front of the fire.

The Medical Man was standing before the fire with a sheet of paper.

Filby sat behind him.

The ghost of his old smile flickered across his face.

Sudden questions kept on rising to my lips.

I could see the silver birch against it.

There were no large buildings towards the top of the hill.

Just as we should travel down if we began our existence fifty miles above the earth's surface.

One lay by the path up the hill.

It so faded into the serenity of the sky.

Below was the valley of the Thames.

In three strides I was after him, had him by the loose part of his robe round the neck.

At intervals white globes hung from the ceiling.

I never found one out of doors.

The presence of ventilating shafts and wells along the hill slopes showed how universal were its ramifications.

To identify these prepositions as locative adessive, we should take the locative prepositional phrase in the sentence and figure out the accurate place of the person or the object. Now we look at some examples. (camera and knapsack are the exact place)

To prove the every locative sema we can change the locative prepositional phrase into an adverb there/here or we can make up question with pronoun where. And we should identify how the object is in the position of locativity. Besides that we can translate them into Uzbek languages.

Locative allative semas represent the direction of the place, person or thing. They represent the movement of placement with locative allative semas, they are presented the motion of place of the objects. Locative allative sema includes different prepositions, such as for, by, into, to, in, on, over, at, towards, against, across.

I would watch for her tiny figure of white and gold so soon as I came over the hill.

'But,' said the Medical Man, staring hard at a coal in the fire.

The rebounding, dancing hail hung in a cloud over the machine.

Necessities had impressed it on the organism.

I saw the sun hopping swiftly across the sky.

We heard his slippers shuffling down the long passage to his laboratory.

Closing her eyes, tightly pressed her face against my shoulder.

Then the Time Traveller put forth his finger towards the lever.

It was very large, for a silver birch-tree touched its shoulder.

We came first into this room.

He looked round the table.

All the old constellations had gone from the sky.

He passed his hand through the space in which the machine had been.

Locative ablative semas represent the person or the thing being far away from the place. They present the movement of being away from the place. Locative ablative sema includes different prepositions, such as out of, from, round, below, above, across, over, opposite, at, in, on.

Filby sat behind him, looking over his shoulder

I could feel it grip me at the throat.

I read my own interpretation in his face.

I felt a tickling on my cheek.

I went up the opposite side of the valley.

But to me she seemed to shoot across the room like a rocket.

'This little affair,' said the Time Traveller, resting his elbows upon the table and pressing his hands together above the apparatus.

He walked slowly out of the room.

Our mental existences are passing along the Time-Dimension with a uniform velocity from the cradle to the grave.

The sun had already gone below the horizon.

As it seemed, from behind me, and away through the wood in front.

Locative translative semas present the movement into one side of an area out of the other part. They represent the movement from one side to another place. Locative allative sema includes different prepositions, such as by, along, through, round, across, over and via.

I felt my way along the tunnel.

We can the spoke of a wheel spinning, or a bullet flying through the air.

A flow of disappointment rushed across my mind.

Locative instrumental semas are used as the weapon or tool. They are represented the noun as the performance of the action. Locative instrumental sema includes different prepositions, such as with, by, to, in, on and by virtue of.

For a moment I hung by one hand.

This line I trace with my finger shows the movement of the barometer.

Research methodology. This study is to investigate locative syntaxemes by using the novel "The Time Machine" by H. Wells, as analysis of locational prepositional phrases in the context and to observe different semas with actual materials. Based on literature review, it explores locative categories, when they are used, how they syntactically differs from each other, and how they can alter the meaning of phrases. Locational prepositional phrases of the novel "The Time Machine" were studied thoroughly whereas it can pragmatically found different meaning of prepositional phrases. Exploring all prepositions phrases, we may come across semantically various meaning in terms of location, motion, direction and instrumentality of the nouns with these prepositions. Collected all information

studied and classified into types. While looking through prepositional phrases with locativity, we identified many phrases with prepositions in this novel analysing them. Locational prepositions in the sentences can have differences in meaning depending

on which nouns they come to. In this novel locative prepositions were found and separated them into the types of locational prepositional phrases from others. The table given below is showed investigation of it.

Prepositions	Prepositional phrases	Locational prepositional phrases	Percentage
At	336	45	13%
In	510	217	42%
On	135	36	26%
In front of	4	3	75%
Before	42	3	7%
Behind	16	9	56%
Across	22	19	86%
Under	32	13	40%
Beneath	4	3	75%
By	96	18	18%
Over	46	16	34%
To	349	46	13%
Above	23	9	39%
Into	111	41	36%
Towards	47	19	40%
Against	32	15	46%
Out of	34	10	29%
From	120	34	28%
Round	32	5	15%
Below	9	2	22%
Opposite	1	1	100%
Along	21	5	23%
Through	49	19	38%
With	213	12	5%
For	206	3	1%
Down	64	34	53%

According to the table, we can see that locative prepositional phrases are a small number of prepositional phrases. It shows that the same prepositions can denote not only location but also time and manner in sentences. So that this research identified locative prepositional phrases and division of locativity in accordance with pragmatic meaning.

Results and analysis. Based on the research, syntactical-semantic features of prepositional phrases with location can come with different meaning, choosing some of locative prepositional phrases by identifying them in the sentences of the novel.

TYPES OF LOCATIVE SEMAS AND THEIR USAGE IN THE NOVEL

From the bar chart, it is obvious that locational prepositions in the usage of the novel “The Time Machine” by Herbert Wells under 25 prepositions denoting locative category witness different trends. Four prepositions in, into, from and on are to be utilised more than others using addressive, allative and ablative types of the locativity in the novel.

We can see that addressive semas are utilised higher rate from others. It come 22 locative prepositions expressing the exact place of a person or a thing. However, some of them (at, in, on) are encountered much more, it shows that they are widespread addressive sema. Allative and ablative semas witness nearly the same quantity of prepositions in 14 and 10 respectively. In allative location such prepositions such as to and down coming more in allative meaning than the others. In ablative location prepositions like from being considered widespread preposition for it. Moreover, traslative and instrumental locative categories also coming with placement of the objects. They are less

encountered in the sentences. In traslative semas mostly used preposition is through being among three prepositions only found in this novel. Instrumental semas are the least found prepositions than all others, they are by and with. The latter is used more than the former in 12 and 5 respectively.

Conclusion. While presenting prepositional phrases with locative semas certain sentences, we can reveal different syntactical-semantic meaning of locative prepositions, which denote various notions in accordance with nouns being considered to include some types of them. Investigating the research by taken several types of locational semas from the novel “The Time Machine” by Herbert Wells is showed distinctive features of these prepositions in using with more, little resemblance with each other. Despite all example being in one book, we can try to give the whole information about locative syntaxeme. By looking through all prepositions related to locativity, we try to define all peculiarities of locational semas.

The analysis is showed similarities and distinctive features of locative prepositions

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